

1 Manuscript submitted to RCR

2 **RESOURCE USE AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: AN EXERGY PERSPECTIVE ON**
3 **ENERGY AND MATERIAL FLOWS AND STOCKS FROM 1900 TO 2010**

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15 **Abstract:**

16 *Energy and materials support food production, maintain and expand material stocks such as*
17 *buildings and roads, and provide services. In this paper, an exergy-based approach is used to*
18 *provide an integrated perspective on the evolution of societal resource flows and stocks. The*
19 *scope of this analysis is from resource extraction (primary exergy stage) to end uses such as low*
20 *temperature heating and illumination (useful exergy stage). From 1900 to 2010, global exergy*
21 *consumption at the primary stage increased from 115 to 903 EJ/year, of which 88-89%*
22 *corresponded to energy flows, including food and feed. Useful exergy flows increased from 9 to*
23 *148 EJ/year, of which 47% in 2010 was contained within material goods. Primary to useful*
24 *efficiency has doubled from 8% to 16%. However, this improvement is far from that which is*
25 *required to achieve climate targets for 2060. The amount of resource flows required per unit of*
26 *economic activity decreased at both the primary (from 58.5 to 17.0 GJ/\$) and useful (from 4.7*
27 *to 2.8 GJ/\$) exergy stages, indicating relative decoupling. The exergy in stocks went from 91 to*
28 *820 EJ. Stock intensity reduced from 46.2 to 15.5 GJ-year/\$ due to a shift in stock composition*
29 *rather than dematerialisation in mass terms. Future research needs to identify the relationships*
30 *between resource flow intensity and stock intensity in order to meet sustainability targets,*
31 *including those linked to future resource demand. The scope could be expanded to include*
32 *additional resources such as water and rare earth metals.*

33

34 **Key words:** material efficiency; material flow analysis; resource efficiency; social metabolism;
35 useful exergy; useful work

36 1. Introduction

37 1.1 Global resource consumption and decoupling

38 Energy and materials are critical for the socioeconomic system, insofar as they are
39 continuously mobilised by society to maintain, operate and expand its material stocks
40 (infrastructure, buildings, vehicles and other machines) as well as to feed and nourish its
41 people and its livestock (Fischer-Kowalski and Weisz, 1999; Giampietro et al., 2011). In turn,
42 the composition, magnitude and patterns of social metabolism determine most of the
43 anthropogenic-derived environmental pressures and impacts (Haberl et al., 2019).

44 Population growth, industrialisation and economic development have all been associated with
45 a rise in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and an accelerated use of natural resources
46 (Krausmann et al., 2018; Schandl et al., 2016a; Van Vuuren et al., 1999). In fact, Wiedmann et
47 al. (2015) demonstrate that for every ten percent rise in GDP, the average national material
48 footprint (i.e. all annual material and energy used by the end consumer) increases by six
49 percent. Therefore, understanding the relationship between energy/material use
50 (consumption and accumulation) and socioeconomic development is essential in achieving
51 absolute decoupling targets (i.e. dematerialisation of the economy) and in identifying where
52 material substitution has occurred (a process referred to by Zhang et al. 2018 as
53 transmaterialisation).

54 At the global scale, the extraction and use of materials and energy has not only continued to
55 grow but has accelerated since the turn of the 21st century (Krausmann et al., 2018). It is
56 estimated that about 140-218 Gt/year of resources will be needed by 2050 (Dittrich et al.,
57 2012; Fischer-Kowalski et al., 2011; Krausmann et al., 2018; Schandl et al., 2016b). In 2010,
58 global resource consumption was 78 Gt, which was a tenfold increase on the values registered
59 in 1900 (Krausmann et al., 2017). For metal ores, the extraction rate more than doubled
60 between 1980 and 2008 (OECD, 2015). This is, in part, because complex mixtures, of up to two-
61 thirds of the periodic table, have steadily entered into the market (Carmona et al., 2017;
62 National Research Council, 2012). The increased complexity and variation of market goods and
63 services is also reflected in Krausmann et al. (2018), who estimated that the share of energy
64 flows (food, animal feed and technical energy) relative to total resource extraction declined
65 from 71 percent in 1900 to 36 percent in 2010. Over the same time period, the share of bulk
66 construction materials, metals and plastics rose from 17 to 52 percent. Such materials are
67 typically used in in-use stocks, which include buildings, road infrastructure and durable goods.
68 The remainder constitutes materials classified as “dissipative use”. These include products
69 such as fertilisers, salt or lubricants. The inherent complexity of the material production chain
70 requires that we understand not only the type and amount of material extraction that is
71 occurring but what materials are destined for and how this links to socioeconomic
72 development (Haberl et al., 2017).

73 1.2 Resource transformation

74 All complex systems, including the world economy, are kept in states far from thermodynamic
75 equilibrium by the continual inflow and transformation of energy and materials (Brown et al.,
76 2011; Chen, 2005; Georgescu-Roegen, 1971; Smil, 2008). The First Law of Thermodynamics

77 dictates that energy can be neither created nor destroyed, whilst the Second Law states that
78 some capacity to perform useful work is irrevocably lost as heat, once energy is transformed
79 from one form into another.

80 The complete picture of the global resource system begins with the primary stage. The latter
81 incorporates resources directly extracted or harvested from Nature (e.g. coal, crude oil, wind
82 power), which are then transformed into the final stage (e.g. refined fuel products or
83 electricity). The output of the last transformation is referred to as useful energy (or useful
84 work). Examples include lighting, low temperature heat and mechanical drive. This stage thus
85 encompasses those flows that come into direct contact with the majority of end users via the
86 provision of energy and material services (Cullen et al., 2011). Such services represent those
87 characteristics or functions that energy and materials contribute to personal or societal activity
88 with the purpose of obtaining or facilitating desired end goals or states (Fell, 2017; Kalt et al.,
89 2019; Whiting et al., 2020). Service examples include “illumination”, “thermal comfort” or
90 “shelter”.

91 Whilst primary, final, and useful energy are convenient categories when restricting the
92 system’s boundaries to energy, categorising resources in this way becomes increasingly
93 difficult upon incorporating material flows and stocks into the analysis. The complexity of
94 material accounting, in terms of the sheer variety of potential compounds and their
95 incorporation into social metabolism, as both stocks and flows, also makes it quite challenging
96 to follow materials from source through to product manufacture, use, recycling and final
97 disposal (Müller et al., 2014; Nakamura, 2011). Another fundamental issue linked to resource
98 accounting, when including both energy and materials into the scope, is unit incompatibility.
99 Energy carriers are typically measured in joules and materials in tonnes. This problematic as
100 their unit mixing would result in an incoherent analysis.

101 **1.3 Exergy analysis for resource transformation**

102 One way to overcome unit incomparability is through the use of exergy. The latter represents
103 the maximum amount of physical work that a given resource can perform relative to a
104 reference system, such as the average concentration of Earth’s crust or the surrounding
105 environment (Szargut, 2005). Those resources that can perform higher quantities of work are
106 said to be of higher thermodynamic quality (Rosen, 2002). For example, one tonne of oil has a
107 higher exergy content than one tonne of coal and therefore a power plant requires less tonnes
108 of oil than coal to produce the same amount of electricity. Likewise, one joule of electricity can
109 be used to produce one joule of work while one joule of heat at 80°C can produce only 0.18
110 joules of work (when the reference environment is at 15°C). The capacity to do work applies
111 equally to both energy and materials, and thus upon conversion into exergy units, one is able
112 to identify and incorporate both resources under a single objective metric and methodology
113 (e.g. Ayres et al., 2006; Valero et al., 2015; Whiting et al., 2017a).

114 Once energy and material units have been converted into their exergy counterparts, it
115 becomes apparent that some exergy is destroyed along the primary to useful value chain.
116 Therefore, some scholars have made the case that it is exergy, *not* energy, that forms the
117 physical basis of economic growth and the added value creation in an economy (Ayres and
118 Warr, 2010; Santos et al., 2018; Serrenho et al., 2014). With each transformation some exergy

119 dissipates along with waste flows. Only a proportion remains at the useful exergy stage. From
120 a physical perspective, this represents the thermodynamically ideal system's minimum
121 requirements, that is to say, if no irreversibilities or unavoidable losses occur.

122 Using exergy for resource accounting is not a particularly common practice (Hernandez et al.,
123 2018). However, as demonstrated by Sousa et al. (2017), an increasing body of knowledge
124 indicates that quantifying exergy from the primary to useful stage improves our understanding
125 of the role energy and materials play in social metabolism. Useful exergy has been increasingly
126 adopted as a metric to assess the functions and services that natural resources contribute to
127 society. One reason for this is that it presents the last step in the resource transformation
128 chain where all societal activity can be measured under one single unit (Brand-Correa and
129 Steinberger, 2017; Kalt et al., 2019). From a strictly thermodynamic perspective, there is only
130 exergy and all exergy is useful. Therefore, the division of exergy into stages is an analytical
131 decision to aid resource accounting, which in turn supports a more in-depth understanding of
132 the key phases involved in production and consumption. Detailed reviews on exergy-based
133 resource analysis can be found in Romero and Linares (2014), Sousa et al. (2017) and
134 Hernandez and Cullen (2019).

135 At the national level, several exergy analyses that consider both energy and common material
136 flows, such as steel, at the primary and the useful stage, have been conducted for selected
137 years and countries (e.g., Chen and Chen, 2006; Ertesvåg and Mielnik, 2000; Gong and Wall,
138 2016; Wall, 1987; Wall et al., 1994). Wall (1987), for example, calculates Swedish exergy flows
139 in 1980, whilst Chen and Chen, (2006) and Zhang et al. (2018) evaluate exergy consumption for
140 China in 2000 and 2012, respectively. However, it appears that no global exergy study for
141 material stocks has been undertaken. This knowledge gap means that we are not able to
142 consistently trace exergy once its extracted from Nature, consumed and/or accumulated and
143 eventually reutilised or destroyed. It is not sufficient to only consider and compare flows if, as
144 aforementioned, society is increasingly dependent on stock for its socioeconomic
145 development. Furthermore, as stocks expands, increasing quantities of exergy are diverted
146 into operations that enlarge, maintain, activate or dispose of that stock, thus contributing to a
147 considerable pressure on the sustainability of future resource demand.

148 Another knowledge gap arises because material flow accounting in primary to useful exergy
149 analyses has predominantly been restricted to fossil fuels for energy purposes and metals,
150 which has meant that the contribution of other types of materials, such as aggregates,
151 phosphate rock and petrochemicals, has been, for the most part, overlooked (Heun et al.,
152 2018; Valero et al., 2018). This practice has led to the sub-estimation of the exergy cost of
153 resource use and resulted in unsustainable forms of resource management (Valero and Valero,
154 2014).

155 **1.4 Aim, originality and scope of paper**

156 This paper's innovative contributions include an exergy account of the different types of
157 energy and material flows and material stocks that constitute global socioeconomic
158 metabolism. This form of accounting is a fundamental step in the acknowledgement and
159 calculation of exergy's role in stock building and the provision of end-uses such as lighting,
160 mechanical drive, and disposable material flows. Based on the exergy approach, which takes

161 both resource quantity and quality into consideration, we scrutinise the interactions between
162 energy flows, material flows and material stocks.

163 The long-term temporal scope (1900 to 2010) of this paper allows us to consider the role of
164 resources in global socio-metabolic transitions, particularly in terms of material accumulation
165 and economic growth. Therefore, the aims of this paper are threefold: 1) Trace global resource
166 consumption and calculate the primary to useful exergy efficiency of resource transformation
167 from 1900 to 2010; 2) Quantify the exergy contained in material stocks and calculate the
168 amount required to maintain, expand and operate stocks; 3) Identify resource dependency
169 trends within the global economy in order to ascertain whether relative or absolute decoupling
170 is occurring, and if so at what level.

171 To achieve these aims, we propose an integrated methodology for a global exergy analysis that
172 integrates energy flows (endo- and exo-somatic) and material flows and stocks under a single
173 unit. The methodology encompasses the production chain from resource extraction (primary
174 exergy) to resource end-uses (useful exergy), including stocks. Based on the transformation
175 chain, we categorise resource flows into “food supply”, “material production” and “technical
176 energy”. “Food supply” flows biologically maintain and support the human population (a form
177 of stock) while technical energy and material production represent those flows that support
178 and maintain the stocks and services that contribute to their standard of living (Krausmann et
179 al., 2018). These categories were selected to allow comparisons with similar ones (see
180 Wirsenius (2003a, 2003b), Nakićenović et al. (1993) and Cullen and Allwood (2010b). We also
181 propose six indicators to assess the long-term resource use and material dependency of the
182 socioeconomic system.

183 The paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 describes the data, methods and assumptions.
184 Section 3 presents the exergy resource consumption and material accumulation results. It
185 provides details on the indicators we used to analyse resource efficiency and stock-flow
186 interactions. Here we discuss the methodological and practical contributions of this paper to
187 the academic community and beyond. It describes the results validation procedure and
188 outlines this study’s methodological limitations. Section 4 presents the conclusions and future
189 work.

190 **2. Data and Methods**

191 **2.1 Exergy Analysis**

192 Exergy has a thermomechanical component that depends on temperature, pressure, velocity,
193 and potential gradients. It also has a chemical component on account of chemical differences
194 relative to the reference environment. The exergy of electricity, heat and mechanical work
195 solely consists of thermomechanical exergy, while the exergy of materials and other energy
196 carriers, such as natural gas and biomass, is mostly chemical exergy. The latter represents the
197 minimal work necessary to produce a material from Szargut’s reference environment, should
198 no irreversibility occur (Gaudreau et al., 2012; Szargut, 2005, 1989). For example, hematite
199 (one type of iron ore) has a chemical exergy of 0.1 MJ/kg whilst crude steel has a chemical
200 exergy of 6.8 MJ/kg. The exergy required to produce steel is much higher than that of iron ore,

201 due to differences in chemical composition and the complexity of the reactions responsible for
202 that composition.

203 For fossil fuels and biomass, chemical exergy is particularly significant at the primary and final
204 exergy stages. Their exact values lie between their respective high and low heating values.
205 Their energy-derived useful exergy depends on the properties of the conversion device and the
206 end use. It is obtained via Second Law efficiency formulas (see Section S.2 of the
207 Supplementary Information), following the transformation of final exergy via end-use
208 conversion devices, such as engines, boilers, ovens or lamps (Heun et al., 2018; Nakićenović et
209 al., 1996). For non-hydrocarbon renewables (e.g., hydropower or photovoltaics), a chemical
210 exergy cannot be calculated, as the energy flow is provided by the thermomechanical
211 component. For non-fuel materials, chemical exergy is particularly relevant, with the exact
212 value dependent on the physiochemical composition of the compound or element. Generally
213 speaking, higher chemical exergy values are associated with those materials that are very
214 concentrated or reactive, meaning that they can easily form chemical bonds with other
215 elements or compounds. Incidentally, these properties often make them more useful for
216 society, as a higher chemical exergy tends to lend itself to a greater range of technical
217 characteristics and functions.

218 Chemical exergy should not be confused with Cumulative Exergy Consumption (CExC), which
219 represents the total exergy cost along the production chain or the lifecycle of a product (Valero
220 et al., 2015). Returning to the iron example, the CExC of hematite is 1.8 MJ/kg whilst that of
221 crude steel is 22 MJ/kg (Carmona et al., 2019; Michaelis et al., 1998). The CExC value will
222 always be higher than its chemical exergy counterpart because it factors in the inefficiencies of
223 current technology.

224 To correctly evaluate the dissipation of exergy within a system, a clearly defined energy and
225 material inventory is necessary, along with the identification of boundaries, operations,
226 processes, final products, sub-products, and wastes. Sousa et al. (2017) proposed the following
227 options to analyse the system: the energy resource and the natural resource approach. The
228 former is limited to energy carriers and the latter can combine both energy and materials,
229 which means that it is most appropriate for the purpose of this research. To ensure that the
230 natural resource approach is methodologically consistent, one should avoid double counting or
231 the incorrect allocation of resources relative to their transformation stage. An example of the
232 first problem can be demonstrated with “heat”. This is because whilst heat can be an output at
233 the useful stage, as is the case for the residential sector, for example, it is not a final output
234 where product manufacture is concerned. In industry, heat drives the processes required to
235 produce final/ intermediate products. The exergy of the latter already embodies this fraction
236 of heat and therefore to account for both final products and high temperature heating is to
237 double count. This issue was already identified by Sousa et al. (2017) who argued that when
238 materials are considered at the useful stage, one should not account for both energy end-uses
239 and material output, because to do so would be a form of double counting. Likewise, the
240 incorrect allocation of resources occurs when ores are accounted for at the useful stage
241 instead of the primary. In the majority of cases, ores provide the raw material for product
242 manufacture and therefore do not represent an end-user interaction, outside of a museum or

243 personal rock collections. For more information regarding energy, material and exergy
 244 conversions please see Section S.2 of the Supplementary Information.

245 2.2 Resource transformation model

246 In this paper, we follow energy and materials from the primary (P_{ij}), to the final (F_{ij}) and useful
 247 (U_{ij}) exergy stages (Figure 1). The role of material stocks (represented by the box " S_t " – purple
 248 square) is significant because they enable further resource extraction and transformation and
 249 facilitate energy/material service delivery (K_i). Resource flows are classified as "technical
 250 energy" (yellow), "food supply" (orange) and "material production" (blue). The exergy in P_{ij} , F_{ij}
 251 and U_{ij} is easier to trace because one flow transforms into another. U_{ij} can be subdivided into
 252 resource flows that directly support a service (U_{ik} – dashed line), resource flows that feed
 253 directly into the production chain (U_p), required for material production ($U_{HTH\&MD}$) or resource
 254 flows that form stock (U_{sb}). There are two major system outflows (grey and black). The energy
 255 outflow (grey) is primarily constituted by exergy lost as heat. The material outflow (black) is
 256 predominantly composed by residuals such as scrap, ash or organic waste. The returning
 257 arrows of useful exergy (e.g. U_p or $U_{HTH\&MD}$) represent that which is either used to maintain the
 258 production process (e.g. lighting used to illuminate the factory) or the proportion which is
 259 directly required for material production and, thus, not consumed by an end user. The return
 260 arrow labelled "Stock building products (U_{sb})" encompasses those materials which do not
 261 constitute dissipative uses.

262
 263 *Figure 1. From primary exergy to energy and material services. Note: Stock-flow-service interaction could be*
 264 *provided via: (1) End-use energy and stock to service (e.g. lighting and lamp into lux), (2) Stock to service (e.g.*
 265 *residential building to m² shelter), (3) Final products and stock to service (e.g. medicine and utensils to days to*
 266 *recovery). U_{ij} : Useful exergy for resource category i obtained through resource transformation chain j ; P_{ij} : Primary*
 267 *exergy for resource category i consumed in resource transformation chain j ; U_{sb} : Intrinsic exergy within stock*
 268 *building products; U_{ik} : useful exergy from resource category i that supports service k (dashed line); U_p : useful exergy*

269 required to maintain the production process. $U_{HTH\&MD}$: high temperature heat and mechanical drive that is directly
 270 required in material production, RE: renewable energy.

271 2.3 Scope and Data

272 Global flows are expressed in terms of annual flows (consumption) whilst global stocks are
 273 stated as accumulated stock for a specified year. We distinguish between three main types of
 274 global resource flows that may be allocated at the primary, final or useful stage. These are
 275 technical energy (exosomatic energy), food (endosomatic energy) and materials (compounds
 276 used for non-fuel purposes). Air and water flows were not included due to the lack of data
 277 regarding end-uses.

278 Table 1 gives an overview of all the resource sub-categories used in this paper for the primary
 279 and useful exergy stages. We do not measure resources at the final exergy stage because we
 280 are not aware of an accessible database that provides this information for the entirety of the
 281 period studied.

282
 283

Table 1. Primary and useful stages of resource categories

Resource categories	Primary exergy		Useful exergy	
	Sub-categories	Characteristics	Sub-categories	Characteristics
Technical energy (exosomatic)	Coal	Fossil fuels	Lighting	Technical energy end-uses
	Natural Gas		Low temperature heat	
	Petroleum		Mechanical drive - transport	
	Biomass - energy (crops and wood)	Renewable energies	Mechanical drive – stationary (e.g. power tools)	
	Geothermal		Other uses (e.g. cooling)	
	Hydro			
	Solar			
	Wind	Others type of primary energy		
	Nuclear			
Food (endosomatic)	Biomass (for food)	Includes food crops, grazed biomass and animal feed	Food intake	Calories ingested
Material	Minerals and metallic ores	Ores, concentrates and aggregates (including sand, rock and gravel).	Stock building use	Includes solid wood, paper, plastics, steel, aluminium, copper, concrete, sand and gravel, glass, bricks, asphalt, other metals & minerals
	Biomass - non energy use	Mainly wood		
	Fossil fuels - non energy use	Includes petroleum and natural gas used as non-energy feedstock	Dissipative uses	Includes petrochemical products (e.g. lubricants, solvent, bitumen) and other minerals/metalloids (e.g. arsenic, bromine, iodine)

284 The global system was selected because of data availability. This removes the potential issue of
 285 geographical boundaries and the resulting methodological challenge that increases the
 286 possibility of double counting when one tries to incorporate trade traceability and
 287 national/regional accounts into the analysis. The main limitation of the global system (and
 288 consequently of this study) is that one cannot go beyond global average values of resource
 289 consumption and accumulation. This means that the large deviations that occur between
 290 countries are hidden and, consequently, overlooked.

291 The world energy data collected and analysed for this paper is taken from the *Primary, Final*
 292 *and Useful Energy Database (PFUDB)* created by the *International Institute for Applied Systems*
 293 *Analysis (IIASA)*. The method used to transform technical energy from primary to useful exergy
 294 can be found in De Stercke (2014). To our knowledge, the PFUDB is the only open access
 295 database that compiles global technical energy flow data from primary through to useful
 296 exergy stage by sector, carriers and end uses from 1900 to 2014. See section S.1.1 of the
 297 Supplementary Information for more details regarding PFUDB and the exergy conversion
 298 factors.

299 The material data required for our long-term global study was taken from various sources
 300 including that compiled in the *global Material Input Stock Output (MISO)* project (presented in
 301 Krausmann et al. (2018, 2017, 2009), the United States Geological Survey yearbooks (U.S.
 302 Geological Survey, 2019), the World Steel Association yearbooks (World Steel Association -
 303 WSA, 2018) and by the FAO (2019). In the MISO approach, global material extraction, stock-
 304 building material flows, the accumulation of material stocks and the resulting domestic
 305 processed output (waste) in tonnes are estimated using a dynamic inflow-driven model
 306 (Wiedenhofer et al., 2019). The MISO database includes estimated worldwide consumption
 307 patterns for 14 common stock-building materials, such as bricks, concrete, sand and gravel,
 308 several metals, paper, plastics, and solid wood. It also contains information for dissipative uses
 309 and food/animal feed. The USGS and WSA databases hold world metal production data from
 310 ore extraction to intermediate products, such as crude steel. The *Food and Agriculture*
 311 *Organization (FAO)* data used is that relating to global food intake. Since all the
 312 aforementioned databases are compiled in mass terms, it is first necessary to convert the units
 313 into their chemical exergy counterparts. See section S.2.2 of the Supplementary Information
 314 for more details.

315 2.4 Resource transformation chains

316 For most resource chains a primary to useful transformation requires various inputs. For
 317 example, diesel (categorised as a technical energy) is required to run the tractors employed in
 318 agriculture and therefore for efficiency calculation purposes, the exergy contained in this fuel
 319 is allocated to “food supply” and not “technical energy”.

320 In this paper, the scope of the resource transformation chains is the following:

- 321 • **Technical energy chain** (or exosomatic energy): this category constitutes those
 322 resources utilised for technical energy end-uses with the exception of those that enter
 323 directly into food supply or material production. The scope of the primary stage
 324 constitutes the energy directly extracted from the natural environment (e.g. biomass,

325 fossil fuels, hydropower, wind, sun, etc.). The final stage includes energy carriers (e.g.
 326 diesel) and the electricity produced from the primary exergy input. It also incorporates
 327 that energy which was not previously transformed, and which thus carries directly
 328 over from the primary stage. The useful stage constitutes lighting, low temperature
 329 heat, mechanical drive (e.g. car motor) and cooling.

330

- 331 • **Food supply chain** (or endosomatic energy): The primary stage includes food crops
 332 and animal feed (grass, non-processed feed crops and forage), and the primary
 333 technical energy and mineral ores (e.g. phosphate rock) required to produce crops and
 334 process them into food or feed. The final stage constitutes plant and animal-derived
 335 products (e.g. fruit and vegetable produce, meat, milk, eggs) and those inputs that
 336 support further food production. These include fertilisers, seeds, pesticides, energy
 337 carriers and crop residues for animal bedding. The category also incorporates those
 338 crops which were not transformed, and which consequently carry over from the
 339 primary stage. At the useful stage and based on the FAO's definition of "dietary energy
 340 supply" (2015, P24), we only take the actual food intake of humans into account. This
 341 is the amount available after non-food uses and crop waste have been subtracted.

342

- 343 • **Material production chain:** The primary stage accounts for the different mineral and
 344 metallic ores according to the state they were in when extracted from the
 345 environment. It also comprises the fraction of raw biomass and fossil fuels not used in
 346 the technical energy or the food supply chain. The final stage considers the
 347 intermediate products of material production and also secondary materials (recycling).
 348 For steel, this may include iron pellets, iron sinter, steel scrap or pig iron. The useful
 349 stage constitutes the final products used in stock building or dissipative uses. Two
 350 common stock building materials are steel and cement. Dissipative flows include
 351 lubricants and salt. To avoid double counting, the exergy of medium/high temperature
 352 heating and the mechanical drive that causes industrial equipment to operate were
 353 not accounted for as useful exergy. Instead only the chemical exergy of final products
 354 was considered (See section S.2.3 of the Supplementary Information for more details).

355 2.5 Exergy-based resource use indicators

356 In this paper, we use four indicators to analyse the role of energy and materials in social
 357 metabolism. Table 2 presents their formulas and accounting observations:

- 358 • **Primary-to-Useful efficiency:** This indicator measures the quantity of exergy that
 359 remains prior to end-uses (TJ) relative to that which was available at
 360 extraction/harvest (TJ). It identifies the exergy loss of the system and sub-systems.
 361 Similar applications from the primary to useful exergy stages in the technical energy
 362 chain have been undertaken by Nakićenović et al. (1996) and Cullen and Allwood
 363 (2010b).
- 364 • **Stock turnover rate:** This indicator represents the annual flow of exergy contained in
 365 stock building materials (TJ/year) per unit of exergy contained in the total stock in a
 366 specific year (TJ). It accounts for the annual fraction of additional resources required to
 367

368 provide stock at a specific level and thus identifies societal dependence on stock
 369 building materials. It also can provide insight on the way in which stock is used (e.g.
 370 the average lifetime of artefacts prior to disposal). Other researchers (e.g. Nguyen et
 371 al., 2019; Wiedenhofer et al., 2015) have undertaken a similar analysis via the annual
 372 requirement of stock maintenance and the annual requirement of stock expansion.

373

374 • **Useful technical exergy intensity of operating in-use stocks** measures the annual
 375 amount of useful exergy derived from technical energy sources (TJ/year) per unit of
 376 exergy contained in stock for a specific year (TJ). This ratio is a proxy that can help
 377 practitioners to analyse the stock-flow interactions involved in delivering services.
 378 Although not in exergy terms, a total primary energy intensity of operating stocks was
 379 calculated by Krausmann et al. (2017).

380

381 • **Resource intensity (MJ/€)** is a conventional measure employed in resource accounting
 382 and policymaking for evaluating energy and material decoupling relative to GDP (see
 383 Fischer-Kowalski et al., 2011, Schandl et al., 2017 and Krausmann et al., 2018 for
 384 example). Other researchers have calculated the long-term energy intensity and
 385 evaluated energy decoupling at the useful stage. Warr et al. (2010) analysed the role
 386 of useful exergy along the technical energy chain for the UK, US, Japan and Austria.
 387 Brockway et al. (2015, 2014) updated this analysis for the US, UK and China whilst
 388 Serrenho et al. (2014) did the same for the EU-15. Regarding developing economies,
 389 Heun and Brockway (2019) calculated the long-term resource intensity at the useful
 390 stage for Ghana, Jadhao et al. (2017) did the same for India and Guevara et al. (2016)
 391 did it for Mexico.

392

393

Table 2. Resource use indicators applied to exergy

Indicator	Formula	Units	Methodological Observation
Primary-to-Useful Efficiency	$\frac{U_{ij}}{P_{ij}}$ (1)	$\left[\frac{J}{J}\right]$	When calculating this efficiency for each category, the denominator should represent the total resource consumption required to produce that category's outflow. This includes those flows that would otherwise be assigned elsewhere. For example, some technical energy is used by industry for material production. This quantity should be accounted as part of the primary exergy that forms the denominator of material production efficiency, and not the denominator for the technical energy efficiency calculation. The same holds true for the technical energy and mineral ores used by agriculture and the food sector, which should be accounted for as part of the primary exergy that forms the denominator of the food supply chain efficiency calculation.
Stock turnover rate	$\frac{U_{sb}}{S_t}$ (2)	$[year^{-1}]$	This indicator measures stock maintenance and expansion as the ratio between stock building products for a specific year to stock accumulated by that year. U_{sb} could be replaced by primary exergy required to produce the stock building products (P_{sb}), in which case it could be used to ascertain the primary exergy cost of maintaining and expanding stocks. A more in-depth differentiation between stock maintenance and stock expansion can be obtained when both annual inflows and outflows are known. However, this step is beyond the scope of the present paper, since system outflows (e.g. waste or recycling) are not evaluated.
Useful technical exergy intensity of operation in-use stocks	$\frac{U_{te}}{S_t}$ (3)	$\left[\frac{J}{kJ \cdot year}\right]$	Useful technical exergy includes the following energy end uses: lighting, mechanical drive (transport and stationary), low temperature heating, and others (e.g. cooling).

Indicator	Formula	Units	Methodological Observation
Resource intensity of economic growth	$\frac{P_{ij}}{GDP_t}$ or $\frac{U_{ij}}{GDP_t}$ (4) $\frac{S_t}{GDP_t}$ (5)	For flows: $\left[\frac{GJ}{\$}\right]$ For stocks: $\left[\frac{GJ\text{-year}}{\$}\right]$	In this paper, this indicator is calculated for the following categories: primary exergy of technical energy and materials, primary exergy of biomass for food, useful exergy of energy and materials, and exergy accumulated in stock. We use global GDP constant to USD 1990, as provided by Maddison (2010) and World Bank (2019).

394 Note: U_{ij} : Useful exergy for resource category i obtained through resource transformation chain j ; P_{ij} : Primary exergy for resource
395 category i consumed in resource transformation chain j ; U_{sb} : Intrinsic exergy within stock building products; U_{te} : Useful technical
396 exergy for energy end uses; S_t : Stock at year t ; GDP_t : Gross Domestic Product of year t .

397

398 3. Results and Discussion

399 3.1 The exergy of resource flows

400 In 1900 global primary exergy consumption was 115 EJ. By 2010 this had increased eight-fold
401 to 903 EJ (Figure 2a). The fastest rate of growth occurred during the 1950s at the dawn of mass
402 western consumerism. This cultural and socioeconomic phenomenon was enabled by the
403 proliferation of oil and gas extraction, which in turn facilitated, among other things, new and
404 exergy intensive forms of road transportation and mass electrification (see Figure S3 of the
405 Supplementary Information). Likewise, useful exergy consumption increased by a factor of 16,
406 from 9 EJ in 1900 to 148 EJ in 2010 (Figure 2b). This substantially bigger jump was caused by
407 technological improvements and an energy transition from coal to natural gas and oil.
408 Together, these two developments drove efficiency gains in the conversion/transformation of
409 primary to useful exergy. The increasing growth patterns shown in Figures 2a and 2b are also
410 noticeable in terms of the metabolic rate, which is the average per capita resource
411 consumption for primary and useful stages. By 1900, primary and useful exergy per capita
412 were 70 GJ/cap/year and 5.6 GJ/cap/year, respectively. In 2010, these values had increased to
413 130 GJ/cap/year (primary) and 21 GJ/cap/year (useful). This means that the higher values did
414 not come from population growth, which increased fivefold between 1900 and 2010, but
415 instead from changes in primary and useful exergy consumption patterns (see Section S.3.1. of
416 the Supplementary Information for more details).

417 While, in general, exergy flows grew throughout the observed period (Figures 2a and 2b), since
418 the 1970s a relative stabilisation in the composition of both primary and useful exergy flows
419 occurred (Figures 2c and 2d). This may indicate a certain maturation of the modern/industrial
420 metabolic system, a phenomenon referred to as “1970s syndrome” by Wiedenhofer et al.
421 (2013).

422 Figure 2c shows the predominance of food and fuels at the primary exergy stage, which was
423 expected due to the high chemical exergy content of both when compared to mineral and
424 metal ores. From 1900 to 2010, the fraction of energy sources in primary exergy, including that
425 derived from food and feed, remained stable at 87 to 89 percent of the total. As shown in
426 Figure 2b, material products are the dominant exergy flow at the useful stage. This is because
427 technical energy inputs become incorporated into material products during their
428 manufacturing process. In relative terms, the useful exergy in stock-building and dissipative
429 use materials remained between 41 and 49 percent of the global useful exergy consumption

430 (Figure 2d). The remaining useful exergy comprised those energy flows involved in the
 431 transformation of the primary energy derived from renewable technologies, fossil fuels or
 432 crops into end uses such as food intake, lighting or mechanical drive. The proportion of useful
 433 exergy in food intake dropped from 43 percent in 1900 to 20 percent in 2010. This relative
 434 reduction reflects the growing demand for mechanical drive utilised in motorised transport
 435 and domestic appliances, rather than a fall in food intake in absolute terms, which actually
 436 increased from 4 to 30 EJ between 1900 and 2010 (Figure 2b).

437

438 *Figure 2. Global exergy consumption from 1900 to 2010. A: primary exergy (PEX) flows. B: useful exergy (UEX) flows.*

439 *C: Primary exergy decomposition. D: Useful exergy decomposition. Note: * This category includes food crops for*

440 *humans, grazed biomass and animal feed. ** This category includes minerals and metallic ores.*

441 Between 1900 and 2010 there was a 11-fold increase in “stock-building” flows and a 53-fold
 442 increase in “dissipative use” flows. The latter reflects the technological innovation that has
 443 occurred since the mass production of petrochemical-based lubricants, paints, oils and
 444 solvents. Krausmann et al. (2018)’s analysis of global material use, which calculated mass
 445 rather than exergy, showed that in absolute terms, “stock-building” flows grew 33-fold whilst
 446 “dissipative uses” grew 9-fold. The difference between Krausmann *et al*’s (2018) results and
 447 those presented in this paper was expected because of the large quantity of aggregates
 448 consumed by society, which although significant in terms of weight are insignificant in terms of
 449 exergy because of their very low chemical exergy value.

450 The validation of these results was undertaken via a comparison with other studies of primary-
 451 to-useful exergy efficiency, including that of Allwood et al. (2011); Chen and Chen (2006);
 452 Cullen and Allwood (2010); Ertesvåg (2001); Ertesvåg and Mielnik (2000); Firth et al. (2019);
 453 Gong and Wall (2016); Nakićenović et al. (1996); Wall (1987); Wirsenius (2003a, 2003b).

454 Further details can be found in Section S.4. of the Supplementary Information.

455

456 3.2 The exergy of stocks

457 A significant proportion of exergy accumulates in active structures (e.g. engines and turbines)
 458 and passive structures (e.g. buildings and infrastructures). Both of these constitute material
 459 stocks. Active stocks enable society to transform flows of primary exergy into useful exergy.
 460 Active and passive stocks combine to allow a person to experience a given service. Figure 3a
 461 shows long-term global stocks in exergy terms. The exergy stored/embodied in stocks
 462 increased from 91 EJ in 1900 to 820 EJ in 2010. Overall stock expansion, when measured in
 463 exergy, amounts to a 9-fold increase from 1900 to 2010, which is much less than the 23-fold
 464 increase in mass calculated by Krausmann et al. (2017). The principal difference between these
 465 two results occurs because of the heavy weight of concrete and aggregates and their relatively
 466 low chemical exergy content. In 1900 the percentage of primary exergy that went into stock
 467 maintenance and expansion was 22 percent of the total, and the remainder went to the other
 468 end uses (food intake, material dissipative uses and energy end uses). By 2010, this fraction
 469 has remained constant over the period.

470

471 *Figure 3. Global stocks from 1900 to 2010 in exergy terms. A: Accumulated stock by main type of materials. B:*
 472 *Accumulated stock composition. Note: Biomass: solid wood and paper; Metals: aluminium, steel, copper and others;*
 473 *Minerals: concrete, sand and gravel, bricks and glass; Petrochemicals: plastics and asphalt.*

474 In mass terms, solid wood was the predominant stock-building material in 1900. It was also the
 475 most significant exergy stock, due to its high chemical exergy value (Figure 3b). By 2010, the
 476 global economy relied on an increasing variety of material stocks, including plastics, steel,
 477 concrete and asphalt, which, along with wood, constituted 80 percent of the total exergy
 478 stock. That said, from 1970 to 2010, petrochemicals for non-fuel purposes (asphalt, plastics)
 479 accumulated at a faster rate than other resources and almost reached parity with biomass.
 480 Sand and gravel were also important commodities, despite their low chemical exergy values,
 481 because of the sheer quantities involved and their essential role in construction. A stock
 482 composition breakdown in exergy and mass terms is presented in Section S.3.3. of the
 483 Supplementary Information.

484 3.3 Resource use indicators

485 3.3.1 Primary to Useful Exergy Efficiency

486 In 1900, only eight percent of primary exergy was carried over to the useful stage; by 2010 this
 487 had increased to 16 percent (Figure 4). This means that while efficiency improved
 488 considerably, 84 percent of exergy (755 EJ) was still destroyed between extraction and service
 489 delivery in 2010.

490 When efficiency is calculated separately for each resource transformation chain, material
 491 production is the most efficient. In 1900, primary to useful exergy transformation had an
 492 efficiency of 18 percent. By 2010 this had reached 26 percent. The better performance
 493 registered for material production was caused by the higher efficiency of high temperature
 494 heating processes, which have the potential to deliver more work than those processes that
 495 come into contact with end users. The lowest efficiency was that of technical energy
 496 conversion, which was four percent in 1900 and 15 percent in 2010. While extraction has got
 497 more costly from an exergy point of view, this has been balanced out by the fact that energy
 498 production and consumption devices have got much more efficient. Similar patterns have
 499 emerged in Brockway et al. (2019) and Brockway et al. (2014). With regard to the food supply
 500 chain, we find that, quite surprisingly, that the primary to useful conversion efficiency
 501 increased from 6 to 11 percent, in spite of the growing significance of animal products in the
 502 human diet. This reflects improvements in the conversion of extracted primary biomass into
 503 food for humans (Krausmann et al., 2013). Among the factors that contributed to these
 504 efficiency gains were the replacement of draught animals by tractors, the shift from grass-fed
 505 ruminants to the more efficient feed converters pigs and poultry and improvements in seed
 506 ratios and harvest indices of crops (see e.g. Harchaoui and Chatzimpiros, 2019; Krausmann,
 507 2004).

508

509 *Figure 4. Primary-to-useful exergy efficiency. Note: Percentage in terms of useful exergy (UEx) divided by primary*
 510 *exergy (PEX).*

511 Although our analysis reveals some improvement in primary to useful exergy conversion
 512 efficiency, overall efficiency still seems to be quite low and efficiency gains appear to have
 513 stalled since the turn of the millennium. This trend has implications for sustainability targets.
 514 Based on the IEA's "Energy Technology Perspectives 2017" (IEA, 2017), global primary exergy
 515 demand across the technical energy and material production chains will, in 2060, reach 928 EJ
 516 under the *Reference Technology Scenario* (business as usual), 731 EJ under the *2°C Scenario*
 517 *(2DS)* and 687 EJ under the *Beyond 2°C Scenario (B2DS)*. 2DS and B2DS incorporate the carbon
 518 dioxide reduction targets set by the Paris Agreement. Useful exergy consumption for technical
 519 energy and material production is expected to be between 183 EJ and 496 EJ. This range is
 520 calculated from the global metabolic rate (see Section 3.1) and the useful exergy intensity of
 521 global economic growth (see Section 3.3.4). Therefore, in order to achieve the exergy
 522 consumption reductions under B2DS, the primary to useful exergy efficiency must increase to
 523 anywhere between 27 and 72 percent by 2060 (see Section S.3.2 of the Supplementary
 524 Information for details).

525 Under all scenarios, one would have to carefully balance the trade-off between materials and
 526 energy to ensure that overall exergy efficiency improves, instead of just energy efficiency at
 527 the expense of materials (Allwood et al., 2012; Carmona et al., 2017; Valero and Valero, 2014).
 528 One way to do this is through the increased reincorporation of recycled material into
 529 production processes, which if done for steel, for example, would improve its resource
 530 efficiency from 26 percent to 39 percent (see Carmona et al., 2019). Another way to gain
 531 efficiency is to decrease dependency on meat products, given the extra exergy losses that
 532 occur when human beings obtain their calories from animal products instead of plants
 533 (Pimentel and Pimentel, 2003; Reijnders and Soret, 2003; Sabate and Soret, 2014).

534 **3.3.2 Stock turnover rate**

535 The stock turnover rate represents the annual flow of exergy contained in stock building
 536 materials per unit of exergy contained in the total stock for a specific year. This indicator thus
 537 reflects the annual throughput of those material flows that society depends on to support an
 538 adequate level of stock for the undertaking of economic activity. Figure 5 shows that the
 539 *annual stock turnover rate* increased from 4.5×10^{-2} to $5.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$, with a peak in 1973
 540 ($6.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$). The exergy values are typically higher (by some 15-50 percent) than their
 541 mass equivalents because of the high chemical exergy values of wood, steel, and plastics (see
 542 Figure S20 of the supplementary information).

543 The exergy cost of the annual stock turnover rate i.e. the primary exergy required to
 544 manufacture stock building products, has grown from 25 to 195 EJ between 1900 and 2010. In
 545 terms of the fraction of annual primary exergy required to manufacture stock-building
 546 materials, relative to the exergy contained in stock, it has declined from 0.28 to 0.23 year^{-1} ,
 547 with the peak of 0.38 year^{-1} registered in 1969 (Figure 5). The difference between the
 548 trendlines of the two indicators, from 1973 onwards, results from improvements in material
 549 production efficiency.

550 The *annual stock turnover rate* is influenced by global events, including economic recessions
 551 and war. For example, it dips in 2008, which corresponds to a lower propensity to produce or
 552 consume goods. This is in turn linked to lower risk factors and a reduction in the willingness to
 553 lend credit, create jobs or spend savings (as is often the case during economic downturns).
 554 Similar occurrences were registered in the 1930s due to the Great Depression, following the
 555 Wall Street Crash in 1929, and again during the 1973 to 1975 global recession, which was
 556 triggered by the 1973 OPEC crisis, another Wall Street stock crash and the socioeconomic
 557 instability which followed the Vietnam War. It was the latter that effectively put an end to the
 558 growth experienced following post-war recovery (WWII). This period of recovery (1946-1973)
 559 was dominated by major infrastructural re-building, which is captured in the increase in *annual*
 560 *turnover rate*. It was also marked by a shift in the general pattern of consumption and
 561 accumulation.

562

563 Figure 5. Annual stock turnover rate. Note: U_{sb}/S_t - Fraction of exergy of annual stock-building flow relative to exergy
 564 of stock (year^{-1}). P_{sb}/S_t - Annual primary exergy required to manufacture the stock-building flow relative to exergy of
 565 stock (year^{-1}).

566 3.3.3 Useful technical exergy intensity of operation in-use stocks

567 The *useful technical exergy intensity of operating in-use stocks* represents the annual amount
 568 of useful exergy that is derived from technical energy sources per unit of exergy contained in
 569 the total stock in a specific year. It identifies the specific combination of the annual minimum
 570 technical energy and stocks that were used to provide the physical foundation for economic
 571 activity. Figure 6 shows that the *useful technical exergy intensity of operating in-use stock* (in
 572 exergy terms) increased exponentially from 10 to 60 J/kJ-year between 1900 to 1970 (which is
 573 higher than the speed of stock growth – Figure 3a), after which it stabilised. This rapid growth
 574 may have been caused by an increased consumption of useful exergy, as living standards
 575 improved across many parts of the globe. These living standards were facilitated by the
 576 proliferation of very energy intensive operating stocks (e.g. heating, cooling, and illumination
 577 of buildings; more passenger and freight kilometres).

578 The end of exponential growth in useful exergy intensity coincides with the OPEC oil price
 579 shock. While stocks continued to grow (although at a somewhat slower pace) the exergy
 580 applied per unit of stock stabilised. This pattern may be due to the technological evolution of
 581 passive systems, saturation effects with respect to certain services, particularly in developed
 582 countries, and a reduction in stock use. A similar trend occurs at the primary stage (see Figure
 583 S19 of supplementary information).

584

585

586 Figure 6. Useful technical exergy (UEX) intensity of operating in-use stocks Note: Useful technical exergy includes
 587 lighting, low temperature heat, mechanical drive – transport and other devices, other uses (e.g. cooling).

588 In 1900 society required 21 MJ/tonne-year of stock. By 1972 this had increased to 92
 589 MJ/tonne-year. Post-1972, *useful exergy intensity of operating in-use stocks* (in mass terms)
 590 gradually declined, reaching a low of 60 MJ/tonne-year by 2009. If one only considers stocks in
 591 tonnes, then it appears that they have become less energy intensive. In fact, since the 1970s
 592 less useful exergy has been required to activate a tonne of stock. However, this gain has only
 593 been made possible because the substitution of traditional construction materials (solid wood
 594 and bricks) with lighter materials that happen to have a higher level of thermodynamic quality
 595 (as indicated by their chemical exergy value). Since the 1970s, the proliferation of light
 596 weighting or fuel-efficiency policies and strategies has caused a greater dependency on lighter
 597 but more chemically complex material elements and compounds (Carmona et al., 2017; Valero
 598 and Valero, 2014).

599 **3.3.4 Resource intensity and relative decoupling**

600 Our results suggest that absolute decoupling did not occur at the global level for primary
 601 exergy flows, useful exergy flows or for stock, in exergy terms (Figure 7). Relative decoupling
 602 between resource consumption and GDP has been observed. Figure 7a shows that the
 603 quantity of primary exergy required to produce one USD(1990) declined by 70 percent
 604 between 1900 and 2010, i.e. from 58.5 to 17.0 GJ/\$. At the primary stage, the resource
 605 intensity of “food” reduced by 85 percent, “materials” by 70 percent and “technical energy” by
 606 44 percent. However, not all resources experienced relative decoupling. For example, the
 607 “hydropower” sub-category went from 1.5×10^{-2} to 0.7 GJ/\$, “nuclear” went from 0 to 0.5 GJ/\$
 608 and the “metallic ores and minerals” went from 0.3 to 0.4 GJ/\$. See Section S.3.4 of the
 609 Supplementary Information for more details. These findings are similar to those observed in
 610 previous long-term trend studies at the global level, when measured, at the primary stage, in
 611 mass terms (e.g. Krausmann et al., 2017, 2009; Schandl et al., 2017).

612 Figure 7b suggests that a relative decoupling also occurred for useful exergy intensity (from 4.7
 613 to 2.8 MJ/\$), albeit at a slower pace relative to primary exergy. Decoupling is particularly
 614 noticeable for “food intake” and “stock building”. Together these two sub-categories,
 615 constituted 87 percent of useful exergy in 1900 and 52 percent in 2010. Two other
 616 subcategories: “lighting” and “mechanical drive – others”, experienced an increase in useful
 617 exergy intensity. This may be explained, in part, by the increased level of electrification and the
 618 proliferation of the tungsten filament incandescent lightbulb. Other sub-categories started to
 619 experience relative decoupling in the 1970s: “mechanical drive - transport”, “materials for
 620 dissipative uses”, “low temperature heating” and “other technical energy uses”. For these
 621 sub-categories, it is difficult to suggest the underlying reasons behind a global change,
 622 especially as regional differences are drawn into an average, which do not capture localised
 623 socio-political and economic transitions. Figure 7d shows a clear coupling between GDP and
 624 useful exergy, as indicated by the similar growth pattern. However, since the 1970s there has
 625 been relative decoupling at the useful stage. In regard to the primary exergy stage, there was
 626 relative decoupling, as a result of improved conversion efficiencies between primary to useful
 627 exergy, as described in Section 3.3.1. These results are in line with Haberl et al. (2020) and
 628 Wiedenhofer et al. (2020), who found that exergy and GDP were tightly coupled and that
 629 absolute reductions of exergy are only likely to be achieved through degrowth strategies and
 630 the enforcement of absolute reduction targets.

631

632 *Figure 7. Resource intensity. A: Primary exergy (PEx) intensity by resource category (expressed as exergy per unit of*
 633 *GDP). B: Useful exergy (UEx) intensity by resource sub-category (expressed as exergy per unit of GDP). 2*: Categories*
 634 *on the right axis. C: Stock intensity (stock per unit of GDP). Note: Global GDP constant to USD 1990, stock intensity in*
 635 *mass term from Krausmann et al. (2017). D: Indexed evolution of GDP, primary exergy, useful exergy and the exergy*
 636 *contained in stocks*
 637

638 The quantity of exergy in stocks required to produce one USD(1990) declined by 70 percent
 639 from 46 GJ/\$·year in 1900 to 15 GJ/\$·year in 2010, which is suggestive of a relative decoupling
 640 (Figure 7c – orange line). This trend differs from that of Krausmann *et al.* (2017), who found no
 641 clear indication of significant long-term relative decoupling between the mass of material
 642 stocks and GDP (Figure 7c – green line). One must be careful when interpreting the exergy
 643 results because what may look like a decoupling in exergy terms may in fact reflect
 644 transmaterialisation, rather than dematerialisation. The latter refers to a reduction of material
 645 weight per unit of GDP whilst the former refers to the process of material substitution. In
 646 1900, when stock was mainly constituted by sand and gravel, bricks and solid wood, the
 647 average chemical exergy per unit of stock was 2.6 MJ/kg. This decreased to 1.0 MJ/kg by 2010
 648 – a change caused mainly by the substitution of wood (which has a high chemical exergy value)
 649 for concrete (which has a much lower chemical exergy), particularly once reinforced concrete
 650 and high-performance concrete became available (see Section S.3.3 in the Supplementary
 651 Information).

652 A decomposition of the stock intensity per type of material shows that six of the twelve
 653 material stock sub-categories have decoupled from economic development, whilst society has
 654 become more dependent on the other six (see Figure S16 in the Supplementary Information).
 655 This is due to the substitution of materials of low exergy values for those with higher ones (e.g.
 656 replacement of solid wood by petrochemicals). Materials with higher exergy values tend to
 657 offer a wider or better functionality than those with lower ones and are therefore favoured by
 658 society. However, they also tend to be scarcer or more reactive, which means that their per
 659 unit extraction results in a higher energy consumption, which also carries a higher

660 environmental cost. It also means that to maintain energy costs at a level where resource
661 extraction remains viable, energy efficiency must improve. This is apparent in the primary to
662 useful efficiency of material production depicted in Figure 4, which has increased despite
663 transmaterialisation.

664 **3.4 Innovations, implications and limitations of this study**

665 There were several innovative aspects in this paper's method. The most substantial
666 contribution is the long-term analysis of the primary to useful exergy embedded in 59 material
667 streams of varying physiochemical composition (fuels, metals, aggregates, biomass, etc).
668 Consequently, the knowledge gap has been addressed on various levels because prior to this
669 study: (1) there had been no analysis of the exergy contained in material stock, which meant
670 that exergy traceability was limited to flows, even though society is increasing dependent on
671 stocks; (2) previous societal exergy analyses were restricted to common metals such as steel
672 and fossil fuels destined for energy purposes. These studies had not taken into consideration
673 non-metals, precious metals or petrochemicals, which are critical components of social
674 metabolism.

675 This paper's results support further exergy research into how technological transitions and
676 socioeconomic development impact the material production chain (and vice versa),
677 particularly in terms of primary to useful transformation efficiency or resource dependency.
678 Our results also provide a more consistent tracing of exergy from extraction through to
679 disposal, which, in turn, offers a more comprehensive understanding of resource use and
680 management. With a more nuanced analysis of resource use, society is in a better position to
681 achieve the sustainable development goals. The research presented here, amongst other
682 things, highlights some of the trade-offs that may get overlooked if sustainable policies focus
683 too much on one specific type of resource or on only one particular link of the production
684 chain.

685 The long-term analysis presented in this paper allowed for an estimation of the exergy cost
686 required to maintain stocks at a specified level (Figure 5). It also enabled the quantification of
687 useful exergy needs associated with stock operation, which is linked to the provision of energy
688 and material services. Together these findings allow for a better identification and
689 understanding of the interrelations among demographic trends, cultural changes,
690 technological advancement, resource consumption or accumulation. Other contributions
691 include the GDP-based stock intensity calculations, which quantified the world's dependency
692 on material accumulation, and the primary to useful exergy efficiency of material production,
693 food supply and technical energy generation. Although GDP is widely used and accepted as an
694 indicator; it does not capture all aspects that contribute to a person's quality of life because it
695 does not accurately account for externalities such as pollution. This points to the need of
696 future research to address resource consumption and accumulation relative to energy and
697 material service provision rather than wealth creation and incomes flows (see Brand-Correa
698 and Steinberger, 2017; Carmona et al., 2020; Haberl et al., 2017; Whiting et al., 2020).

699 The main limitation of this paper is that by assessing the global system the large deviations
700 that occur between countries remain hidden. This has ramifications for sustainable resource
701 management because it fails to identify and thus address (or celebrate) local issues (or

702 successes) that either reduce or increase a given population's access to services. Another
 703 shortcoming results from the lack of data availability regarding water end-uses (e.g. cleaning,
 704 food intake and thermal regulation). Although this issue will not have affected the "food
 705 supply" transformation chain, which was calculated via food intake values (the water in it
 706 containing a low chemical exergy) the material production chain values would have been
 707 impacted, as certain ore extraction and processing methods require copious amounts of water
 708 and thus the exergy contained in the total amount of that water is proportionally much higher
 709 than the exergy of the ore (Whiting et al., 2017b). Other data-based limitations include those
 710 linked to the chemical exergy of rare earth elements and other scarce metals and the final
 711 stage exergy values for materials. The lack of a final exergy database means that the tracing of
 712 exergy from extraction to disposal remains incomplete. This paper's results could have also
 713 been improved by including "passive stock" and "active stock" sub-categories to better
 714 understand the role of materials in social metabolism. The limitations regarding exergy values
 715 for rare earths means that the exergy cost at the useful stage will have been underestimated
 716 for the stock building category. In this regard, our result could also be compared to additional
 717 thermodynamic analysis approaches such as emergy (Amaral et al., 2016), the exergy
 718 replacement cost (Valero et al., 2015) or cumulative exergy extracted from the natural
 719 environment (Dewulf et al., 2007), so as to account for the exergy required by Nature to create
 720 what society uses as resources (Whiting et al., 2017b, 2017a).

721 **4. Conclusions**

722 Since 1900, absolute exergy consumption at the primary stage has increased eight-fold, which
 723 partially negated the exergy savings that occurred due to improved resource efficiency along
 724 the production chain. At the useful stage this increase has been even higher at sixteen-fold,
 725 which is indicative of the intensified energy and material demands required to maintain the
 726 standards of living experienced globally in 2010, relative to 1900. In per capita terms, this
 727 trend is similar. At the primary stage, exergy consumption doubled and at the useful stage it
 728 quadrupled. This means that the average world inhabitant in 2010 had greater access to
 729 lighting, motorised transport, electrical appliances (as captured by mechanical drive) and
 730 various single-use materials than their 1900 counterpart.

731 Although primary to useful exergy efficiency almost doubled from 1900 to 2010, there is
 732 considerable potential for improvement. In 2010, 84 percent of the global exergy present at
 733 extraction/harvest was lost upon reaching the useful stage. This means that only a small
 734 fraction (16 percent) of the total exergy available resulted in every product and service
 735 provided in 2010. Regarding the efficiency of each resource transformation chain, the biggest
 736 primary to useful exergy efficiency increase was for technical energy, which went from
 737 approximately 3 to 15 percent. The food supply and material production chain improved from
 738 approximately 6 to 11 percent and from approximately 16 to 24 percent, respectively.

739 This paper has added to an increasing body of knowledge that quantitatively demonstrates
 740 that the long term accumulation of material stocks is a major factor in socioeconomic
 741 development (e.g. Chen and Graedel, 2015; Haberl et al., 2017; Krausmann et al., 2009; Rogich
 742 et al., 2008; Weisz et al., 2015). This behaviour manifests in the way that society expends
 743 effort and resources to build, enlarge and maintain social metabolism (Carmona et al., 2017).

744 In absolute terms, the exergy diverted into stock-building materials grew 11-fold over the
 745 period. This is indicative of the fact that both society and individuals are expending more
 746 effort and demanding more resources to build, enlarge, and maintain what they already have.
 747 In per capita terms the exergy contained in stocks doubled. The useful technical exergy
 748 intensity for stock operation and service delivery also increased from 8 to 60 J/kJ stock per
 749 year. This suggests that 2010 living standards were supported by stocks that require
 750 considerable energy inputs to function and support service delivery. Further research needs to
 751 be undertaken to better understand the stock-flow-service interaction and the potential for
 752 improvements in energy, material, and service efficiency.

753 The resource intensity of economic growth decreased at both the primary and useful exergy
 754 stages, which is indicative of relative decoupling. The latter is occurring at a lower rate for
 755 useful exergy than primary. Other researchers have put forward the case that there are
 756 minimum exergy requirements for economic development (e.g. Santos et al., 2018; Warr et al.,
 757 2010), although the range is unclear. Our results suggest that there is further potential for
 758 exergy savings per unit of GDP (although not for absolute decoupling) given that, for many
 759 end-uses, resource intensity is still decreasing. The main problem/limitation is that any gains
 760 made in exergy efficiency will be negated while society is increasingly demanding considerable
 761 quantities of highly complex material stock to the detriment of the environment (Nuss and
 762 Eckelman, 2014). There is also scope for testing the added value of primary to useful exergy
 763 analysis to ascertain resource flow and stock intensity at the national level. This may lead to
 764 insights regarding the trajectory of relative or absolute decoupling in different countries and
 765 could provide empirical support for an environmental Kuznet curve linked to resource
 766 intensity. In terms of stock, it appears that transmaterialisation has been a leading cause of the
 767 reduction in resource intensity in exergy terms. Future research must better ascertain the link
 768 between stock intensity and resource efficiency, given that the potential for material
 769 substitution is subject to the longevity of stock and environmental limits.

770

771 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

772 None.

773 **Acknowledgements**

774 L.G.C. acknowledges the financial support of Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) and
 775 MIT Portugal Program through the grant PD/BD/128038/2016. L.G.C. acknowledges the
 776 support of Colciencias. K.W. acknowledges the financial support of the UCLouvain FSR Post-doc
 777 2020 fellowship. D.W. and F.K. acknowledge funding by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF),
 778 Project Nr. P27590 and by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's
 779 Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No 741950).

780 **Authors contributions**

781 L.G.C.: Conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, methodology, writing - original draft,
 782 review & editing. K.W.: Conceptualization, formal analysis, writing - original draft, review &
 783 editing. D.W.: formal analysis; writing - review & editing; F.K.: data curation, formal analysis;

- 784 methodology, writing - review & editing; supervision. T.S.: formal analysis; methodology,
785 writing - review & editing; supervision.
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